

Interdisciplinary Anesthetic Management in Prolonged Ischemic Priapism: Report of Glanssectomy Under Neuraxial Anesthesia Technique

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Ischemic priapism is a urological emergency characterized by a painful and prolonged erection secondary to venous outflow obstruction of the corpora cavernosa. Timely treatment is essential to prevent irreversible tissue damage and permanent erectile dysfunction. Evidence regarding optimal anesthetic management in urgent penile surgery remains limited.

Objective: To describe the anesthetic approach using subarachnoid block with titrated sedation in a patient with refractory ischemic priapism, as well as the perioperative course.

Clinical case: A 45-year-old male patient, without chronic diseases, presented with ischemic priapism of 24 hours’ duration. Due to lack of response to conservative measures, glanssectomy with exploration of the corpora cavernosa was performed under subarachnoid block with hyperbaric bupivacaine and dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant, in addition to intravenous sedation. The procedure was completed with hemodynamic stability, adequate analgesic control, no intraoperative complications, and rapid recovery. The postoperative course was favorable, without adverse events, with partial preservation of erectile function.

Discussion: The clinical evolution is consistent with evidence supporting the use of regional anesthetic techniques in penile surgery, which offer advantages such as effective analgesia, reduced need for general anesthesia, and faster recovery. The use of intrathecal dexmedetomidine contributed to deeper analgesia and cardiovascular stability. Early intervention was key to limiting cavernous tissue damage.

Conclusion: Subarachnoid block with titrated sedation represents a safe and effective anesthetic alternative in emergency surgeries for ischemic priapism, promoting hemodynamic stability, optimal analgesia, and accelerated recovery. This case provides relevant evidence on the value of regional techniques in urgent urological procedures and underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to optimize functional outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Ischemic priapism, regional anesthesia, subarachnoid block, intrathecal dexmedetomidine, urological emergency, glanssectomy, hemodynamic stability, titrated sedation

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INTRODUCTION

Priapism is an infrequent urological condition, with an estimated incidence of 0.3 to 1.0 cases per 100,000 inhabitants per year, but with severe functional consequences if not treated in a timely manner. More than 90% of cases correspond to the ischemic or low-flow type, characterized by a prolonged, painful erection unrelated to sexual stimulation, secondary to obstruction of venous drainage from the corpora cavernosa. This condition leads to blood stasis, acidosis, and

tissue anoxia, making ischemic priapism a true urological emergency. If not resolved within the first 4 to 6 hours, cavernous tissue may suffer irreversible structural damage with fibrosis and permanent erectile dysfunction, significantly affecting the patient’s quality of life.^{1,2}

The differential diagnosis between ischemic and non-ischemic priapism is based on correlation of clinical findings, medical history, and blood gas analysis obtained from the corpora cavernosa. The ischemic type presents with dark

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blood, hypoxemia, hypercapnia, and metabolic acidosis, reflecting the absence of circulatory exchange. Given its urgent nature, the therapeutic goal focuses on achieving rapid detumescence, relieving pain, and preserving erectile function.^{2,4}

Treatment follows a stepwise approach, beginning with aspiration of cavernous contents and irrigation with normal saline, combined with intracavernosal administration of alpha-adrenergic agonists such as phenylephrine. According to guidelines from the American Urological Association (AUA) and the Sexual Medicine Society of North America (SMSNA), if these measures fail, distal corporoglanular shunts, such as the Al-Ghorab shunt, or cavernosal tunneling procedures should be performed. In refractory cases, proximal shunts or even early penile prosthesis placement may be considered in chronic or irreversible situations.^{3,4}

Surgical treatment of ischemic priapism is based on restoring blood flow by creating a communication between the corpora cavernosa and the glans penis, allowing drainage of deoxygenated blood and reperfusion of the tissue. Burnett and Pierorazio (2009) described a modification of the Al-Ghorab shunt known as the “corporal snake maneuver,” which involves the progressive retrograde insertion of a dilator through the shunt opening to disrupt intracavernosal septa and allow more complete drainage of clots and stagnant blood.¹ This technique has proven effective in refractory cases, optimizing tissue reperfusion and reducing the risk of cavernous necrosis or fibrosis, thereby justifying surgical exploration of the corpora cavernosa in prolonged or recurrent cases.^{3,4,5}

From an anesthetic perspective, management of these patients represents a significant challenge. These are emergency procedures performed in patients with severe pain, anxiety, risk of bleeding, and potential hemodynamic alterations secondary to stress or the use of vasoactive agents. The choice of anesthetic technique should aim to ensure adequate pain control, cardiovascular stability, and rapid postoperative recovery. In this context, neuraxial blockade associated with titrated sedation represents an effective and safe option, as it provides high-quality anesthesia and analgesia, minimizes intravenous drug requirements, and allows maintenance of spontaneous ventilation and intraoperative hemodynamic control. Additionally, it facilitates immediate neurological assessment and offers excellent postoperative analgesia, reducing opioid use and related adverse effects.^{3,6}

Despite numerous surgical reports describing cavernous shunts and their variants, the literature specifically addressing anesthetic management in procedures such as glansctomy or exploration of the corpora cavernosa for ischemic priapism remains scarce. In this context, the present clinical case contributes to the available evidence by describing the successful management of a patient with refractory ischemic priapism using neuraxial anesthesia with sedation, highlighting its feasibility, hemodynamic stability, and

adequate intraoperative analgesia in an emergency urological setting.

CLINICAL CASE

This is the case of a 45-year-old male patient, Mexican mestizo, employed as a construction worker, who presented to the emergency department with a persistent and painful erection of 24 hours' duration, without associated sexual stimulation. He reported progressive pain, penile rigidity, and lack of response to local measures, which prompted immediate evaluation by the urology service. He had no family history of hematologic or genetic diseases and did not use chronic medications. As a relevant personal history, he reported an unremembered urological surgery performed 20 days earlier under regional anesthesia, without complications. He denied chronic degenerative diseases but reported alcohol consumption (12 large beers per week), active smoking (one pack per week), and a history of recreational use of cocaine, methamphetamine (“crystal”), and crack, although without recent use. His diet was high in carbohydrates and low in vegetables, with little physical activity.

On initial evaluation, he was hemodynamically stable, with blood pressure of 110/60 mmHg, heart rate of 60 bpm, respiratory rate of 14 breaths per minute, and oxygen saturation of 99%. He was conscious and oriented, with no airway abnormalities; chest and abdominal examinations were unremarkable. Genital examination revealed a fully erect, turgid, and painful penis, with a firm, board-like glans and rigid corpora cavernosa, findings consistent with ischemic priapism. Based on the typical clinical course, pain intensity, and penile rigidity, a clinical diagnosis of ischemic priapism was established. Cavernous blood gas analysis and imaging studies were not performed due to the evident presentation and the need for urgent intervention. Other causes such as non-ischemic priapism, trauma, or pharmacological etiologies were ruled out, and a diagnosis of idiopathic ischemic priapism was concluded.

Given the lack of response to conservative measures, the urology service indicated surgical management consisting of glansctomy with exploration of the corpora cavernosa. The procedure was performed under subarachnoid block with titrated sedation and noninvasive monitoring. The patient was placed in the sitting position; asepsis and antisepsis of the dorsolumbar region were performed, followed by infiltration with 2% lidocaine (3 cc) at the L3–L4 intervertebral space. A short 25-gauge Whitacre needle was used, obtaining clear cerebrospinal fluid, and hyperbaric bupivacaine 12.5 mg with dexmedetomidine 4 µg was administered without evidence of toxicity. After a latency period of seven minutes, a sensory level up to T6 was confirmed and surgery was initiated. Sedation was maintained with oxygen at 2 L/min, propofol at 50 µg/kg/min (total dose 320 mg), midazolam 3 mg, and fentanyl 125 µg intravenously. As adjuvants, ondansetron 8 mg, dexamethasone 8 mg, and ketorolac 30 mg were

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administered. The fluid balance was -500 mL, with an estimated blood loss of 200 mL and urine output of 50 mL. Throughout the procedure, vital signs remained stable, with mean arterial pressure >65 mmHg, heart rate between 65 and 90 bpm, respiratory rate $12-14$ breaths per minute, and oxygen saturation between 99% and 100% . No intraoperative complications occurred. At the end of surgery, the patient was transferred to the post-anesthesia care unit under spontaneous ventilation, hemodynamically stable, with blood pressure $103/68$ mmHg, heart rate 58 bpm, respiratory rate 12 breaths per minute, SpO_2 100% , Aldrete score 9 , RASS 0 , VAS 0 , and Bromage $4/4$.

The postoperative course was uneventful. The patient did not experience post-dural puncture headache, nausea, pain, or neurological alterations. He remained hospitalized for three days with favorable evolution, without bleeding or infection at the surgical site, and with partial recovery of erectile function. He tolerated the anesthetic procedure excellently and did not present adverse events or hemodynamic complications. He was discharged in good general condition with outpatient follow-up by the urology, psychology, and psychiatry services, remaining stable at subsequent evaluations.

This case highlights the efficacy and safety of subarachnoid block with dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant in emergency urological surgery for ischemic priapism, achieving adequate analgesia, cardiovascular stability, and rapid recovery without the respiratory or hemodynamic risks associated with general anesthesia. It also underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary approach and psychological support in patients with a history of substance use, promoting comprehensive and satisfactory recovery.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present case can be contextualized within the available evidence on ischemic priapism and its associated etiologies. Ördök et al. (2024) analyzed 40 cases of ischemic priapism and reported that patients with sickle cell disease had a higher risk of comorbidities, increased recurrence, a greater incidence of cavernous fibrosis, and a significantly higher need for penile prosthesis placement, mainly due to delays in seeking medical care. Although our patient did not have an underlying hematologic disease, this study reinforces the critical importance of symptom duration as a predictor of irreversible cavernous damage.⁷ In this case, intervention at 24 hours through glanssectomy and cavernous exploration under neuraxial blockade allowed limitation of structural damage, avoidance of major complications, and partial preservation of erectile function. This comparison underscores the relevance of timely care and coordinated anesthetic-surgical management to improve the functional prognosis of ischemic priapism.

Regarding anesthetic techniques, the literature consistently supports the role of regional anesthesia in penile surgery.

Ghiringhelli and López (2021) described a case of radical penectomy in which the spinal-epidural combination, together with multimodal analgesia, provided excellent intraoperative and postoperative pain control, reduced opioid use, and promoted better psychological adaptation. Blockade of the sacral roots and the pudendal nerve decreases central sensitization and may reduce the risk of chronic postoperative pain.⁹ These findings are consistent with those observed in our case, where a subarachnoid block with dexmedetomidine facilitated hemodynamic stability, deep analgesia, and rapid recovery without anesthetic complications.

The use of regional techniques as an effective alternative to general anesthesia has also been demonstrated in comparative studies. Anand et al. (2024) showed that partial penectomy under local anesthesia with penile nerve blocks is safe, reduces anesthetic and surgical time, and provides postoperative outcomes comparable to those achieved with spinal or general anesthesia. These data support the rationale for employing regional techniques in penile surgery, particularly in emergency settings where general anesthesia may increase respiratory or hemodynamic risks.¹⁰ In the present case, the choice of neuraxial blockade allowed a safe procedure with excellent tolerance and accelerated recovery. Additionally, recent studies have evaluated the impact of spinal anesthesia on male sexual function. Allameh et al. (2023) demonstrated that although spinal anesthesia does not alter penile length, it may be associated with transient erectile dysfunction during the first postoperative month, a finding that resolves by three months.⁶ This information is valuable when considering the potential functional effects of anesthetic techniques. However, our patient did not experience transient erectile dysfunction or neurological alterations, which may be attributed to appropriate titration of the block, the absence of predisposing comorbidities, and relatively early intervention.

Furthermore, the literature shows that refinement of penile nerve blocks can enhance the safety of regional anesthesia. Hsu et al. (2013), in a series of 1,481 penile surgeries, demonstrated that dorsal nerve, cavernosal, and perineal plexus blocks, combined with acupuncture, reduced anesthetic complications, decreased the need for general anesthesia, and promoted faster recovery.⁸ This supports the current trend toward more targeted regional techniques, particularly in sensitive surgeries such as penectomies and corporoplasties. Consistent with these findings, the anesthetic management of our patient confirmed the usefulness of subarachnoid block as a safe and effective technique.

Despite the favorable outcomes, it is important to acknowledge the specific limitations of the technique used. Subarachnoid block may cause hypotension, inadvertent high block, bradycardia, partial failure, or positioning difficulties in patients with severe pain. Although none of these events occurred in our patient, they should be considered when selecting the anesthetic technique, especially in emergency

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scenarios or in patients with significant comorbidities. Likewise, intrathecal dexmedetomidine, while effective, still lacks large-scale studies evaluating its long-term safety in genital surgery.

The clinical implications of this case are relevant, as it demonstrates that even in the context of a urological emergency, carefully planned regional anesthesia can offer significant advantages in terms of hemodynamic stability, pain control, functional preservation, and rapid recovery. It also reinforces the importance of individualized anesthetic selection and a multidisciplinary approach that includes emotional and psychological support.

This case further highlights the need for future research directly comparing regional techniques (spinal vs dorsal nerve block vs combined blocks) in emergency penile procedures, evaluating their true impact on erectile function, and establishing protocols to define the role of adjuvants such as dexmedetomidine in neuraxial anesthesia for genital surgery.

Among the strengths of the present case are the multidisciplinary management, appropriate anesthetic selection, achieved hemodynamic stability, absence of adverse events, and partial preservation of erectile function despite delayed presentation. A relevant limitation was the absence of cavernous blood gas analysis and validated

erectile function questionnaires; however, these limitations did not affect clinical decision-making or anesthetic–surgical outcomes.

The main lessons from this case include the importance of early recognition of priapism, the need for immediate access to appropriate surgical and anesthetic approaches, and the utility of regional techniques as safe strategies with rapid recovery in penile surgery. Additionally, the value of emotional support in patients undergoing procedures with high psychological impact is emphasized.

From the patient’s perspective, he reported immediate pain relief, satisfaction with recovery, and gratitude for partial preservation of erectile function. He expressed feeling safe throughout the anesthetic process and highlighted the value of postoperative psychological support, reinforcing the importance of a patient-centered approach rather than a pathology-centered one.

Overall, this case provides valuable evidence supporting neuraxial blockade with titrated sedation as a safe, effective, and functional alternative in the anesthetic management of emergency urological penile conditions, with direct implications for anesthetic practice in contexts where functional and emotional preservation of the patient is paramount.

Figure 1. Clinical appearance of the ischemic glans prior to surgical intervention, showing partial necrosis and violaceous–black discoloration compatible with prolonged venous congestion and advanced tissue damage due to ischemic priapism.

Figure 2. Surgical site immediately after glanssectomy, showing the penile stump and adequate hemostasis following resection of necrotic tissue.

CONCLUSION

The present case demonstrates that regional anesthesia, specifically subarachnoid block with titrated sedation, represents a safe, effective, and functional alternative for emergency urological procedures such as glanssectomy and cavernous exploration in cases of ischemic priapism. This technique provided optimal analgesic control, hemodynamic stability, and rapid recovery, without intraoperative or postoperative complications. Early intervention contributed to limiting cavernous tissue damage and preserving part of the erectile function, highlighting the importance of timely and coordinated management between anesthesiology and urology. This case reinforces the value of individualizing the anesthetic strategy, considering regional techniques even in urgent genital surgeries, and providing comprehensive emotional support. The experience gained underscores the need for further research into the impact of regional anesthesia on sexual function and long-term functional outcomes in this type of procedure.

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Ethical considerations: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, the interventions performed, and the potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

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